

Low-Cost and Highly Efficient Automated Agribot using IoT

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Abstract— Agribot is a robot developed using ARM LPC2148 which performs elementary functions like ploughing, sowing, water sprinkling, leveling and pesticide sprinkling simultaneously. It operates in automatic and manual mode. IoT enables the utilization of TCP/IP web-app to control agricultural processes. IR sensor detects the obstacle during its movement. Temperature is sensed for any variations to ensure proper growth of plant. The optimal temperature range is set to 22°C-33°C. The threshold resistance for determining moisture level is 700. The pump is switched on automatically based on moisture level. pH sensor is used to detect the pH of soil. Most of the crops grow well in slightly acidic conditions of pH range 5.5-7.0. NPK value required for choosing appropriate fertilizer is determined. The amount of NPK is displayed in percentage in the format “N: 25 P: 25 K: 50”. The crop suitable for the particular type of soil is determined.

Keywords—Agribot; seeding; GPS;IoT;ploughing; leveling; sensors; TCP/IP tool; Wi-Fi; Zigbee

Introduction

Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy. It determines to a large extent the growth of the nation. Raising the agricultural production is critical as it plays dominant role in country's wealth. As population is increasing, need for agricultural goods is increasing. The traditional farming methods are unacceptable. Farmers are under huge pressure as are not getting sufficient yield in spite of the labour and resources invested. A cost effective solution has to be developed to overcome the situation. In present days, many robots have been developed for agricultural activities. Rapid advancements are taking place due to the latest technologies being used. IoT is an emerging technology which finds its use in real time applications. IoT can connect the farmer through the web application from anywhere. Wi-Fi module is used which connects to the TCP/UDP tool in Android phone. Image processing unit is used to process database to the algorithm which can give suggestions to farmers using ZigBee.

In our proposed system, a multifunctional agricultural robot (Agribot) is developed which performs basic functions like digging, seed dispensing and leveling. Agribot makes the field work easy and saves time. It has

additional functions like water and pesticide sprinkling. Pump is automated through the use of moisture sensor. The farmer is connected through the web-app which provides timely alerts to farmers. The Agribot can be utilized in both automated and manual mode and assists the farmer instead of just being a replacement.

The system also supports functions like soil testing to know its nutritional values. It intimates the farmer about the fertilizers and crops appropriate for a particular type of soil. Other functions include temperature sensing and determining pH value to ensure the healthy growth of crop. Solar power is used as an alternative source of power. It provides an energy-efficient solution.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various literatures have been discussed about the design of Agribot. A prototype of agribot is developed which is used for sowing. It measures seed spacing as input to sow the seeds precisely. Mild steel is used for chassis to handle more weight. Solar power can be utilized as alternative to the lead-acid battery being used [1]. An energy-efficient agribot is developed for precision agriculture. The robot is implemented for performing tasks such as seed monitoring by sensing parameters such as moisture, temperature and humidity. The robot is built using XBee. It uses the resources precisely when required by the crops for wastage reduction [2]. An autonomous agribot is being developed which is GPS and vision based. Vision system is used for navigation. Stereo vision sensors detect obstacle up to 5m. Suspension system is used to avoid skidding. Multiple robots can be utilized to reduce time using swarm technology [3]. An agribot is developed which sends alerts to the farmer via GSM. To track the location GPS technology is used. Webcam is used to send live updates to server [4]. An agribot is developed based on Bluetooth technology. Bluetooth module is used to send the commands through android application. Weed control is integrated [5]. A hexapod agribot is developed which moves in multiple directions without turning its body. It avoids the obstacles using proximity sensor. A sensor is integrated in its under body to sense whether sowing is done at a given location [6]. An agribot is

designed using Atmega microcontroller. It is enhanced using various sensors for sensing temperature, soil moisture, and humidity. Water pump is integrated for automatic irrigation [7]. An agribot is proposed which performs all the processes in farming simultaneously. This robot is implemented using master controller and a gripper arm. IR sensor is used to detect barriers in the path of the agribot [8]. An electromechanical agribot is implemented using Arduino. It uses ultrasonic sensor to detect the fence wall of the field [9]. An agribot is designed which works on the concept of precision agriculture. The spatial distance for each type of crop is programmed to the robot using MATLAB [10].

II. COMPONENTS

A. Hardware

ARM LPC2148 is the brain of agribot. Various functions in the field are enabled through microcontroller. LCD provides user with the interface to select modes and display various parameters. A voltage regulator IC maintains the 5V output voltage constantly. The agribot is powered by 12V lead acid battery. Solar panel is used as alternate power source. DC motors are fixed to the chassis of the robot for the movement. Motor drivers are used to drive the motors in desired directions. The motor driver used is a L293D IC called H-Bridge. Using H-Bridge motor can operate in either direction. Relay is a switch operated by small currents. Various sensors are used in Agribot which produces very small currents that can be activated using relays. Two channel relay is used for charging the pump and control delay. LM35 senses temperature for adequate crop growth. Moisture sensor is used to measure the water levels in soil. The water pump is switched on automatically when the moisture levels of soil goes higher than the threshold value set for each type of crop. IR sensor is used for detection of obstacle. ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi enabled module. AI-THINKER modules are the first series of modules made with ESP8266. pH sensor is used to detect pH value of soil. Zigbee CC2530 module is highly integrated 2.4GHz transceiver used to communicate with controller.

B. Software

KeilµVision4 is used to communicate with the controller along with Flash Magic. MATLAB is used for detection of NPK values of soil using SVM algorithm.

III. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AGRIBOT

Block diagram of the agribot model is shown in fig.1. It consists of ARM LPC 2148, Power Supply (Solar/battery), Motor Drivers, Pumps, Moisture Sensor, Robot Assembly, Wi-Fi Module, IR Sensor, Temperature Sensor, pH Sensor and ZigBee. The Microcontroller used is ARM LPC 2148. It is integrated with various components. Agribot is powered by either battery or solar panel. The 220VAC is stepped down to 12VAC using step-down transformer. Rectifier converts 12VAC to 12VDC. The voltage regulator used converts 12VDC to 5VDC and maintains this value constantly.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of Agribot

Agribot works in two modes. The user can select automatic or manual mode. If command “A” is selected through web-app automatic mode is selected. The web-app used is TCP/UDP tool in smart phone. The basic agricultural functions are performed simultaneously. The flowchart of agribot is shown in fig 2.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of automatic mode

If manual mode is selected, each process such as ploughing, seeding, leveling, water sprinkling, obstacle detection, moisture level sensing, pesticide sprinkling,

temperature sensing and pH detection is done according to the user command.

Two DC motors are placed on the wheels of Agrirobot fixed to chassis. Robot assembly's simultaneous movement is controlled by motor drivers. H Bridge is used for the movements of robot in forward, backward, right and left directions. With L293D, two motors can be run simultaneously.

IR sensor is used to detect the obstacles in the path. When the obstacle is detected, the agrirobot takes 90° shift and continues its process. This helps the robot to plough in straight rows by detecting the boundaries of field.

Two pumps are used. One pump is used for water supply. Water is pumped based on the moisture level of the soil. Moisture sensor is used to detect the moisture content of the soil. When the probes of the sensor are inserted into soil, it conducts electricity in presence of moisture. It is possible due to movement of free ions and hence there is decrease in resistance. The analog values obtained are from 0 to 1023. The threshold is set to 700. The ideal moisture levels of soil for growth of crop is between 400-700. If the moisture content is greater than the threshold, the water pump is switched on automatically. The soil moisture levels are checked frequently to maintain adequate moisture levels.

The second pump is used for pesticide sprinkling. Pesticide is sprinkled through small holes made on the pipe fitted to the pump. This avoids harmful pesticide coming in contact with bare hands of farmer. Two-channel relay is used for controlling the pump.

Temperature sensor is used for measuring temperature and the values are displayed on LCD. The optimal temperature range for the proper growth of plant is from 22°C to 33°C. If the temperature lies within this range, a message normal temperature is displayed on LCD. If temperature goes beyond the optimal range, an alert is sent to farmer. Temperature is measured frequently to keep a check on fluctuations. pH sensor is used to sense the pH level of the soil. The crops grow well in slightly acidic conditions and ideal pH range is between 5.5 and 7. When the pH level of soil is lesser than 7, the message 'Acidic' is displayed on LCD screen. If the pH level goes beyond 7, the message 'Basic' is displayed.

Zigbee is used for communication with controller. Determination of NPK value is essential for knowing the suitable crop for soil. Datasets of soil images are used for both testing and training stages. The soil contains various amounts of nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium. Nitrogen makes the soil green, phosphorous leaches bluish color and potassium leaves yellowish blue. Each soil will have a particular NPK value. Soil features are extracted using image processing. Grey-scale image and adaptive histogram images are obtained. Classification of images to a particular set is done using SVM algorithm to obtain NPK value. Amounts of NPK are displayed on LCD in terms of percentage. The message "N: 25 P: 25 K: 50" is displayed. Based on the NPK values, type of crop for particular soil is found out.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An agrirobot is developed which performs functionalities such as digging, sowing, leveling, water and pesticide sprinkling. It uses sensors to detect and monitor temperature, pH and moisture level of soil. The battery and solar powered agrirobot is depicted in fig.3.

Fig.3. Agrirobot System

Fig.4. Selection of auto mode

The desired mode of operation can be selected by toggling the switch in the system. The automated mode is selected as shown in fig.4. The system starts performing all the functions simultaneously row wise when a single command 'A' is given through the app.

Fig.5. Selection of manual mode in robot

The selection of manual mode of agrirobot is as shown in fig.5. The system performs a single operation at a time depending on the command sent by the user through the app.

Fig.6. Display of IP address

The agrirobot and PC are configured by matching their IP addresses and specifying port numbers as shown in fig.6. A connection established is between the Wi-Fi module ESP8266 and the agrirobot. The system communicates with the TCP/IP app of the android phone.

Fig.7. Commands given in TCP/IP app

The particular activity to be performed is given as a command through the app by the user as shown in fig 7.

Fig.8. Detection of pH value

Fig.8 shows the value of the pH that is detected using the pH sensor and displayed on the LCD when the command H is selected. When the pH level of soil is lesser than 7, the message 'Acidic' is displayed. If the pH level goes beyond 7, the message 'Basic' is displayed on the LCD screen.

Fig.9. Forward movement of Agrirobot System

Agrirobot moves forward when command 'F' is given through the app as shown in fig 9. Backward movement of agrirobot is initialized by sending command 'B'.

Fig.10. Detection of moisture level of soil

Fig.10. Shows that when the command 'M' is selected, the moisture sensor detects the amount of moisture content of the soil. The threshold for moisture level of soil is set to 700.

Fig.11. Pump switched On

If the moisture content in soil is detected to be greater than the threshold value of 700, then the pump is switched on automatically for pumping water as shown in fig.11. The system checks and switches off the pump if the moisture content is found to be sufficient.

Fig.12. Detection and display of temperature

The temperature is checked using the temperature sensor and value is displayed when the command 'T' is sent through the app. If the temperature lies within the optimal temperature range of 22°C to 33°C, then the message 'Normal temperature' is displayed on the LCD as shown in fig.12. An alert is given to farmer for abnormal temperature when the temperature goes beyond the normal temperature of 33°C.

Fig.13. Detection of object by IR sensor

If there is any obstacle in the field, it is detected by the IR sensor. The message 'Object detected' is displayed on the LCD screen as shown in fig.13. The robot takes 90° shift to right and moves forward to avoid the obstacle.

Fig.14: Digging operation performed by the agrirobot

The digging operation performed by the agrirobot is displayed on LCD as shown in fig.14. When the command 'D' is selected by the user in the TCP/IP app, the system ploughs the land in straight rows. The agrirobot performs similar operations like sowing, leveling and pesticide sprinkling.

Fig.15: Original Soil image

Fig.15. shows the soil image which is given as input to MATLAB.

Fig.16. Grayscale and adaptive histogram images

When a particular soil image is given, feature extraction is done. The grayscale and adaptive histogram images are formed as shown in fig.16.

Various properties of image such as entropy, skewness and kurtosis are calculated. SVM algorithm classifies the given soil image into a particular class of soil. Since NPK detection depends on the type of soil, its value is determined.

Fig.17. Display of NPK values

The amount of NPK in percentage is displayed on LCD as shown in fig.17. It intimates the farmers to use the suitable fertilizers based on NPK value.

Fig.18. Display of suitable crops

The crops suitable for a particular type of soil based on NPK value are displayed on LCD as shown in fig.18.

V. CONCLUSION

A multifunctional agribot is designed and developed which can perform multiple agricultural operations simultaneously. The TCP/IP web-app is used to give commands through Wi-Fi and guide the agribot to perform movements like ploughing, dispensing of seeds, levelling, water and pesticide sprinkling. The robot uses sensors to detect the temperature, pH and moisture content of the soil and their values are displayed on the LCD screen. The IR sensor detects obstacle and commands the robot to change its path. This prototype is energy efficient as it uses solar energy as an alternate power source. The system supports additional features like detecting NPK values of the soil. The constant rise in the demand for agricultural products is fulfilled by use of Agribot. There is reduction in wastage of resources and there is no requirement of labour. The system is also cost effective as it is only a one time investment for farmers. The designed

prototype works successfully with high accuracy and can be incorporated for present and future agricultural practices.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

In future venture, video monitoring can be for the field to be monitored more accurately. Implementation of advanced sensors would control the motion of the robot even under worst field conditions. Use of ultrasonic sensors and cameras for measuring the area covered by the robot and weight of the material for levelling improves the performance of the robot. More advanced and fast system can be developed with more focus on implementation of right mechanical parts and their designing. Quad copter can be used for pesticide spraying and fertilizers to increase land fertility.

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